

Polarographic Reduction of Thorium and Uranium in 2, 2'-Dimercapto Diethyl Ether Media

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The polarographic reduction of Thorium and Uranium in presence of 2, 2'-dimercaptodiethyl ether has been found to be irreversible and diffusion-controlled in 40% ethanolic media. The values of kinetic parameters-transfer coefficient (α) and formal rate constant ($K_{f,h}^{\circ}$)-for the electrode reactions have been determined at ionic strength $\mu = 0.1M$ ($NaClO_4$) under various conditions of temperature and ligand-concentration by applying Koutecky's method as extended by Meites and Israel. The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS for the systems calculated at 25° are also reported.

IN continuation of the earlier work on polarographic behaviour of several mercapto compounds and their metal complexes carried out by Saxena and coworkers¹⁻⁵, this communication reports the polarographic reduction of thorium and uranium in presence 2, 2'-dimercapto diethyl ether, the determination of kinetic parameters under various conditions and the values of change in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) for the electrode reactions. The literature is, however, silent on these investigations.

Experimental

2, 2'-dimercapto diethyl ether (referred herein as $R(SH)_2$) was supplied by Evan's Chemetics, Inc, New York and other chemicals used were of Anal-R(BDH) grade. Triton X-100 and $NaClO_4$ were used as maximum suppressor and supporting electrolyte respectively. Both systems are studied in 40% ethanolic media.

C-Vcurves were drawn on a manual polarograph in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen using S.C.E. as the reference electrode. The capillary had the following characteristics: $m = 2.652$ mg/sec, $t = 2.65$ sec and $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.253$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/6} in a solution containing 40% ethanol and 0.1M $NaClO_4$. The values of kinetic parameters were determined from the polarograms of the solutions containing 0.2mM Th^{4+} or 2.0 mM UO_2^{2+} , 0.1M $NaClO_4$, 0.002% Triton X-100 and various amounts of $R(SH)_2$ using Koutecky's method as extended by Meites and Israel.

Results and Discussion

Thorium and Uranium ions in presence of 2, 2'-dimercapto diethyl ether produce well defined cathodic waves in neutral ($pH = 7.0$) and $HClO_4$ ($pH 3.4$) media respectively and hence the present systems

have been investigated at the above pH values.

The plots of $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ for each system were straight lines but the values of their slopes were not in agreement with the theoretical value indicating the irreversible nature of the electrode reactions in both cases.

Effects of Hg-pressure, temperature, concentration of $R(SH)_2$ and metal ion: With increase in the height of Hg-column, it was observed that i_d changed linearly with $h_{eff}^{\dagger}$ and the values of $i_d/h_{eff}^{\dagger}$ were almost constant indicating the diffusion controlled nature of the waves which was further supported by the

Fig. 1. Plots of i_d vs. $h_{eff}^{\dagger}$ for thorium (curve 1) and uranium system (curve 2).

the values of temperature-coefficient of i_d (1.77 and 2.34% per degree for thorium and uranium systems

respectively) and the linear relationship between i_d and metal ion concentration. The plots of i_d vs $h_{\text{eff}}^{1/2}$ and temperature are shown in Figs. 1 and 2

Fig. 2. Plots of i_d vs. temperature for thorium (curve 1) and uranium system (curve 2).

With increase in ligand concentration, $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards more negative potential and i_d decreased in each case indicating the complex formation between metal ion and the ligand.

Determination of kinetic parameters: Since thorium and uranium reduce irreversibly at d.m.e. in 2,2'-dimercapto diethyl ether, the values of transfer coefficient (α) and formal rate constant ($K_{f,h}^0$) for the electrode reactions have been determined under various conditions by Koutecky's method⁶ as extended by Meites and Israel⁷ using the following standard equations:

$$E_{d.e.} = E_{1/2} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{i_d - i} \quad \dots (1)$$

where

$$E_{1/2} = -0.2412 + \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 K_{f,h}^0}{D_0^{1/2}} \quad (2)$$

and are summarised in Tables 1 and 2. The effect of $R(\text{SH})_2$ -concentration on αn and $K_{f,h}^0$ may be attributed to the change in $E_{1/2}$ and i_d with the change in ligand-concentration. With increase in temperature, the rates of the electrode processes increase and half-wave potentials shift towards less negative potential showing the easier reduction of the complexes at higher temperatures which is in accordance with the irreversible nature of the electrode reactions.

Thermodynamic functions: The values of free energy of activation (ΔG), enthalpy of activation (ΔH) and entropy of activation (ΔS) of the electrode

TABLE 1. VALUES OF αn AND $K_{f,h}^0$ AT VARIOUS $[R(\text{SH})_2]$ FOR THORIUM AND URANIUM SYSTEMS

Conc. of $R(\text{SH})_2$ (mM)		i_d (μA)		$-E_{1/2}$ (V)		αn		$K_{f,h}^0$ (cm/sec)	
Th	U	Th	U	Th	U	Th	U	Th ($\times 10^{34}$)	U
4.0	10.0	4.40	6.30	1.380	0.400	1.585	0.686	5.53	1.50×10^{-5}
8.0	20.0	4.35	6.10	1.384	0.447	1.575	0.704	6.57	3.61×10^{-6}
12.0	40.0	4.32	5.95	1.387	0.502	1.571	0.713	6.59	7.09×10^{-7}
16.0	60.0	4.30	5.80	1.390	0.535	1.564	0.723	7.46	2.49×10^{-7}
20.0	80.0	4.28	5.70	1.392	0.560	1.557	0.742	7.60	9.47×10^{-8}

TABLE 2. VALUES OF αn AND $K_{f,h}^0$ AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES FOR THORIUM AND URANIUM SYSTEMS

Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	i_d (μA)		$-E_{1/2}$ (V)		αn		$K_{f,h}^0$ (cm/sec)	
	Th	U	Th	U	Th	U	Th	U
15	4.35	—	1.371	—	1.594	—	6.43×10^{-24}	—
20	4.75	5.90	1.352	0.575	1.485	0.722	2.55×10^{-31}	0.84×10^{-7}
25	5.25	6.75	1.350	0.540	1.445	0.638	1.78×10^{-30}	6.76×10^{-7}
30	5.70	7.50	1.313	0.524	1.408	0.571	1.16×10^{-29}	2.34×10^{-6}
35	6.10	8.25	1.292	0.510	1.372	0.531	1.06×10^{-27}	5.30×10^{-6}
40	6.70	8.90	1.272	0.508	1.355	0.516	6.85×10^{-27}	6.96×10^{-6}

reactions for both systems have been determined at 25° by using the standard equations as explained earlier³ and are as follows:

Thermodynamic function	Thorium	Uranium
$\Delta G(\text{Kcal/mole})$	47.35	15.30
$\Delta H(\text{Kcal/mole})$	82.10	18.77
$\Delta S(\text{Cal/mole/deg})$	116.60	11.64

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